

The cytochrome P450s CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 confer resistance to flupyradifurone in the green peach aphid *Myzus persicae*

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ABSTRACT

The green peach aphid, *Myzus persicae*, is an economically important crop pest that has evolved resistance to numerous insecticides used for control. Recent research has shown that populations of *M. persicae* in Greece have evolved resistance to flupyradifurone, a butenolide insecticide that acts as a reversible agonist on insect nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs). However, the genetic mechanisms underpinning resistance remain unclear. Here we used transcriptomic profiling in combination with *in vivo* and *in vitro* functional approaches to show that flupyradifurone resistance in *M. persicae* is conferred by enhanced expression of the P450 genes *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4*. High levels of flupyradifurone resistance were observed in *M. persicae* clones from Greece and France, including in a clone that predates the registration of this insecticide. Synergist bioassays with piperonyl butoxide, an inhibitor of P450s, suggested resistance was mediated, in part, by enhanced P450 activity. Subsequent, transcriptome profiling identified several P450s that were overexpressed in the resistant *M. persicae* clones compared to susceptible clones. Functional characterisation of these P450s revealed that only *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4* confer resistance *in vivo* and metabolise flupyradifurone *in vitro*. In two clones with extremely high levels of resistance to flupyradifurone, overexpression of these P450s was accompanied by the R81T mutation in the $\beta 1$ subunit of the nAChR, known to confer resistance to neonicotinoids and cross-resistance to flupyradifurone. These findings provide new insight into the mechanisms of resistance to flupyradifurone and reveal how generalist P450s can be preadapted to confer cross-resistance to diverse insecticides.

1. Introduction

The green peach aphid *Myzus persicae* (Hemiptera: Aphididae), is an economically important pest of many agricultural and ornamental plant species. This species causes damage through direct feeding and the transmission of plant viruses (Bass et al., 2014). The intensive use of insecticides to control *M. persicae* has led to widespread resistance, with reported cases to over 80 unique active ingredients (Mota-Sanchez and

Wise, 2025). Consequently, *M. persicae* has become a model of insecticide resistance evolution in insects, with studies identifying a diverse range of mutations leading to resistance in this species (Bass et al., 2014).

Flupyradifurone is a systemic insecticide acting as a reversible agonist of nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChR), binding to the same molecular site on the receptor as sulfoximines and neonicotinoids (Nauen et al., 2015). However, it belongs to the butenolide class, a

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chemically distinct subgroup of nAChR agonists (IRAC classification group 4D). Flupyradifurone can be applied both as a spray and a seed treatment and is xylem mobile, providing effective protection to the entire plant. These characteristics make this insecticide highly effective at controlling sucking pests such as whiteflies and aphids (Jeschke et al., 2015). Initial assessments of the efficacy of flupyradifurone against neonicotinoid-resistant insects showed good effectiveness against certain imidacloprid-resistant strains of whiteflies and aphids (Nauen et al., 2015). However, following its commercial introduction in 2016, resistance monitoring efforts soon started to report flupyradifurone-resistant populations of whitefly *Bemisia tabaci*, in mainland China (Wang et al., 2020a, 2020b). Initial investigation of the underlying mechanism of resistance in this species implicated metabolic processes, with esterases and cytochrome P450s suggested to be playing a key role (Wang et al., 2020a). A more recent study of field-collected resistant strains of *B. tabaci* functionally linked overexpression of the cytochrome P450 CYP6CX4 with decreased field efficacy of flupyradifurone in China (Zhang et al., 2024).

Flupyradifurone was first registered in Greece in 2018. However, subsequent monitoring of the sensitivity of *M. persicae* populations in Greece to this and other insecticides, identified clones showing moderate (~20–80) to high (~100–1900) resistance ratios to flupyradifurone just three years after its introduction (Papadimitriou et al., 2022). Notably, resistant clones also exhibited moderate cross-resistance to acetamiprid, a neonicotinoid insecticide used to control *M. persicae* (Papadimitriou et al., 2022). In regards to the latter, field-evolved resistance to neonicotinoid insecticides in *M. persicae* is attributed to two primary mechanisms: i) the R81T point mutation in the $\beta 1$ subunit of the nAChR, and, ii) overexpression of the cytochrome P450 CYP6CY3, as a result of gene amplification and microsatellite polymorphism in promoter sequence (Bass et al., 2014; Troczka et al., 2021). In the context of flupyradifurone resistance, a clone of *M. persicae* carrying the R81T mutation, that showed >1100-fold resistance to the neonicotinoid imidacloprid, was found to exhibit 200-fold resistance to flupyradifurone (Bass et al., 2015). Furthermore, genome-edited *Drosophila melanogaster* engineered to carry the R81T mutation exhibited modest (6.9-fold) but significant levels of resistance to this insecticide (Homem et al., 2020). Collectively these findings clearly demonstrate that the R81T mutation confers cross-resistance between neonicotinoids like imidacloprid and flupyradifurone. However, Papadimitriou et al. recently identified clones of *M. persicae* with high levels of resistance to flupyradifurone in the absence of the R81T mutation (Papadimitriou et al., 2022). This finding clearly indicates that other uncharacterised mechanisms in *M. persicae* confer resistance to this insecticide.

The objective of the current study was to investigate the mechanism (s) conferring resistance to flupyradifurone in *M. persicae*. Using transcriptomic profiling in combination with functional approaches we reveal the role of the P450 genes CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 in resistance.

2. Methods

2.1. Insect clones

Two flupyradifurone susceptible clones were used in this study, 4106A collected from potatoes in Scotland in 2000 and clone 37 collected from oilseed rape in Italy in 2015. Resistant clones comprised 5191A and 18KarTob03 collected from tobacco in Greece in 2007 and 2018 respectively, 19TyrP02, 20MelP02B and 20MelP04 collected from peach in Greece in 2019, 2020 and 2020 respectively, clone 5 collected from peach in France in 2009 and clone 67 collected from peach in Greece in 2017. Clones were maintained in small plastic cups or Blackman boxes at 18 °C on individual Chinese cabbage leaves, *Brassica napus* L var *chinesis* cv Tip-Top (clones 4106A, 5191A, 37, 5 and 67) or *Solanum tuberosum* L. (clones 18KarTob03, 19TyrP02, 4106A, 5191A, 20MelP02B and 20MelP04) under a 16:8h light:dark regime.

2.2. Chemicals

Technical grade flupyradifurone (purity ≥ 98 %) and piperonyl butoxide (PBO, purity ≥ 99 %) were purchased from Sigma-UK (Sigma-Aldrich, UK). Flupyradifurone metabolites, FPF-(difluoroethyl)amino-furanone (FPF-AF), FPF-5'hydroxy (FPF-OH) and FPF-difluoroethanamine (FPF-DFEA) were of analytical grade and obtained in-house (Bayer AG, Monheim, Germany).

2.3. Insecticide bioassays

To determine the sensitivity of aphid clones to flupyradifurone, full dose response bioassays were conducted using a leaf-dip methodology. For clones 5, 37, and 67, a stock solution of 100000 mg/L flupyradifurone was made up in acetone and diluted to 7 concentrations: 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100, 1000, and 10000 mg/L using 0.02 % (v/v) Triton X-100 solution in distilled water. Cabbage leaf discs 37 mm in diameter were soaked in the relevant concentration of flupyradifurone or 0.02 % Triton X-100 solution as a control, allowed to dry naturally and placed inverted on 1 % agar in plastic pots. Ten L4 stage nymphs were then placed on each leaf with four biological replicates used per clone, per treatment.

For the synergist bioassays, aphids were pre-treated with 0.25 μ l of 500 mg/L PBO solution in acetone topically applied at least 4h prior to the leaf dip bioassays. Acetone alone was used as a control.

Bioassay data with flupyradifurone for the clones 4106A, 5191A, 18Kartob03, 19Tyrp02 and 20MelP04 were generated by the same research team in a previous study (Papadimitriou et al., 2022), using a slightly different method. Young adult apterous aphids were tested against 9 to 10 different concentrations (including only water as control) of water dispersions of flupyradifurone (Sivanto Prime® SL; Bayer Hellas A.G., Marousi, Greece). A minimum of 20 aphids per concentration were used for each clone. Young leaves of cabbage, *Brassica oleracea* L., were dipped for 10 s in the solutions, dried for 30 min in a fume hood and placed (abaxial surface upwards) on 1 % agar in plastic dishes (3.5 cm diameter). The dish lids had a hole of 2 cm diameter covered with fine muslin. Five aphids were placed in each plastic dish with a fine paint brush.

For the synergist bioassays we used the leaf-dip method described above. PBO was dissolved in a mixture of N,N-dimethylformamide and emulsifier W (3:1 by weight) and subsequently diluted with distilled water to the required concentrations (50–1000 mgL⁻¹, depending on the aphid clone). Aphids were pre-treated with PBO using the leaf-dip method, for at least 3 h. In preliminary assays these concentrations caused <2.5 % mortality in the clones tested. Then the aphids were treated with 10–12 concentrations of flupyradifurone (including control) using the leaf-dip method.

In all bioassays, the aphids were kept post-treatment at 23–24 °C under a 16:8h light:dark photoperiod. Mortality was assessed at 72 h.

Lethal concentration 50 % (LC₅₀) values and 95 % confidence intervals were calculated using probit analysis as implemented in PoloPlus (LeOra Software). Resistance ratios (RRs) were calculated relative to the corresponding LC₅₀ value for the susceptible reference clone 4106A.

The synergistic ratio (SR) was calculated by dividing the initial LC₅₀ by the LC₅₀ post-synergist treatment.

2.4. Transcriptome profiling

Transcriptomic data for 4106A (SRA accession SRR10199550) and 5191A (SRR10199530) were published previously (Singh et al., 2020) and deposited in NCBI BioProject: PRJNA574571. Additional replicated transcriptomes (n = 3–4) were generated for 18KarTob03, 19TyrP02, 5, 37 and 67 in the current study (SRR35859322 - SRR35859340). For this, four replicates of age-synchronised 20 adult aphids (three replicates for 18KarTob03) were collected and flash frozen in liquid N₂. Total RNA was extracted using the Isolate II RNA Mini Kit (Meridian Bioscience) and sent to Novogene UK for sequencing using paired Illumina 150 bp

reads.

To investigate the role of target-site mechanisms in resistance we first mapped RNAseq data of each clone to genes encoding nAChR subunits, to identify potential target-site alterations associated with resistance. Sequence alignments were manually inspected using the Geneious software (Biomatters).

Transcript abundance was estimated from RNA-seq data using Salmon (Patro et al., 2017) in mapping based mode in conjunction with an index generated G006 transcriptome and genome (Singh et al., 2021), with the genome used as the decoy sequence. Unnormalised abundance values were imported into R (R Core Team, 2018) using tximport (Soneson et al., 2016) and analysed using DESeq2 using the default median-ratio estimation of size factors and adjusting for batch effects using sva (Leek et al., 2012; Love et al., 2014). For this, pairwise contrast comparisons were made between individual resistant and susceptible clones to identify differentially expressed genes that may underlie resistance to flupyradifurone, as well as a broader resistant vs susceptible comparison using all resistant/susceptible clones as replicates. Significance thresholds of adjusted p-value <0.05 and absolute log fold-change >0.5 were used for all comparisons. Gene expression figures were generated using R packages ggplot2 (Wickham, 2009) and complexheatmap (Gu, 2022).

Gene datasets showing significant upregulation and downregulation in resistant clones were analysed for GO term enrichment using Fisher's Exact Test in OmicsBox (Biobam) with default settings. Enrichment results were reduced to their most specific terms prior to output and figure generation.

2.5. Transgenic fly bioassays

Flies expressing *CYP6CY3* (GenBank accession KF218356) and *CYP6CY4* (GenBank accession NP_001352549.1) were generated in a previous study (Singh et al., 2020). ORFs of new candidate genes (*CYP380C37* - GenBank accession PX521109, *CYP6DA1* - GenBank accession PX521107, *CYP6DA2* - GenBank accession PX521108) were obtained from the G006 reference genome and synthesised by Twist Biosciences (USA) and subcloned into pUASattB40 between *EcoRI* and *XbaI* sites (GenBank: EF362409.1). Plasmid DNA was purified using the Qiagen mini-prep kit (Germany) and sequence verified using Eurofins Sanger sequencing service (Germany). Transgenic lines were generated using the PhiC31 system by the fly facility at the University of Cambridge. Transgenes were introduced into the germline of a *D. melanogaster* strain, containing an attP landing site on chromosome 2 (attP40) and the phiC31 integrase gene under the control of the vasa promoter on the X chromosome (y w M (eGFP, vas-int, dmRFP)ZH-2A; P [CaryP]attP40)(Markstein et al., 2008). The obtained lines were balanced and verified via PCR and Sanger sequencing as described previously (Manjon et al., 2018). In total 4 transgenic lines were generated with the following transgenes *CYP6DA1*, *CYP6DA2*, *CYP380C37* (Genbank accession numbers as above) and *CYP380C40* (OM677847.1). To activate transgene expression, virgin female flies of the Act5C-GAL4 strain (y[1] w[*]; P(Act5C-GAL4-w)E1/CyO) were crossed with males carrying the specific P450 gene of interest. Adult female progeny of the crosses were used in bioassays to assess the susceptibility of individual lines to flupyradifurone. The control line was generated by crossing the actin strain with a line transformed with an empty pUAST plasmid. Each bioassay was composed of 7 concentrations (600, 780, 1014, 1318, 1713, 2227 and 2896 mg/L) of insecticide made up in a 50 % acetone: water solution overlaid on 1 % agar in a clear plastic vial. Each concentration was replicated 4 times with 20 individual flies per vial. Additional Kaplan-Meier survival analysis of transgenic *Drosophila* lines expressing *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4* were performed by exposing the fly lines expressing these P450s (and the control line) to 1800 mg/L flupyradifurone and assessing mortality over a 120 h period.

Flies were kept at 24 °C 16h:8h cycle, and the mortality was scored

after 72 h. The LC₅₀ and 95 % confidence intervals were calculated using probit analysis in LeOra Software PoloPlus version 1.0.

2.6. Quantitative PCR

qPCR was used to, i) verify the successful activation of transgene expression in recombinant flies and, ii) examine the expression of candidate P450 genes in flupyradifurone resistant and susceptible clones of *M. persicae*. For the former, RNA was extracted from 5 adult female flies using Isolate II RNA mini-kit (Meridian Bioscience) and the cDNA was synthesised from 1000 ng of total RNA using RevertAid cDNA Synthesis kit using random hexamers (ThermoScientific, USA). All qPCR reactions were done in 15 µl reactions using SYBR Green JumpStart Taq Readymix (Merck) and 0.25 µM of each primer. *RPL32* and *SDHA* were used as reference genes (all primer sequences are detailed in Table S3) and 1 ng of cDNA. Transgene expression was compared to the parental lines not crossed with the driver. Data were analysed according to the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001). Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism v10.3.1 (Dotmatics). For qPCR of *M. persicae*, RNA was extracted from pools of 10 adult females (4 biological replicates per clone) and cDNA synthesised as above. PCR was performed as above using the primers detailed in Table S3 and *actin* and *para* used as reference genes. Data was analysed as above.

2.7. In vitro expression of CYP genes

All aphid P450s and cytochrome P450 reductase (CPR) of *M. persicae* ORFs were synthesised by Twist Biosciences (USA) into the pTwistEntr vector. All cells used in the experiment were maintained in an antibiotic and serum-free suspension culture. Recombinant baculoviruses were generated using the BaculoDirect C-term kit (ThermoScientific, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol in Sf9 cells. Final viral titre was quantified using the ELISA method utilising the gb64 primary antibody (Abcam, UK) and Horseradish peroxidase conjugate (Abcam) before visualisation using TrueBlue peroxidase substrate (Merck, Germany). Protein expression was done by co-infecting High Five cell culture (2 × 10⁶ cell/ml) with P450 and CPR viruses at a multiplicity of infection (MOI) ratio of 3 to 1. Ferric citrate and δ -aminolevulinic acid hydrochloride were added to a final concentration of 0.1 mM at the time of infection and 24 h after to boost endogenous heme production. Cells were harvested 56 h post-infection, and the microsomal fraction prepared as described previously (Schenkman and Jansson, 2006). The protein content of samples was determined using Bradford reagent (Merck, Germany) and bovine serum albumin as a reference.

2.8. Competitive inhibition assays

Extracted microsomal membranes containing individual recombinant P450s were tested for specific P450 activity using fluorescent model substrates. Briefly, 50 µg of total protein was incubated in a sodium/potassium buffer pH 7.4 with 50 µM of either 7-Methoxy-4-(trifluoromethyl)coumarin (MFC) and 7-(4-methoxybenzyloxy)-4-trifluoromethylcoumarin (MOBFC) (ThermoScientific) in the presence of NADPH in a total volume of 100 µl. The activity was measured against NADPH-negative wells. The generation of fluorescent product was measured in a kinetic mode for 1 h at 25 °C using a Gemini M2 spectrophotometer (Molecular Devices, USA) with excitation-emission settings of 410:535 nm (MFC) and 405:510 nm (MOBFC).

To determine if P450 enzymes of interest interact with flupyradifurone, inhibition kinetics experiment were performed as adapted from Haas and Nauen (2021) with fluorescent substrate conditions as described above and a series of increasing concentrations of flupyradifurone 100, 200, 500, 1000, 2000, 4000 and 5715 µM. The results were processed and plotted as dose-dependent relative activity, and statistical analysis performed, using GraphPad Prism v10.3.1 (Dotmatics).

2.9. Flupyradifurone metabolism assays and UPLC-MS/MS analysis

Recombinantly expressed CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 in isolated microsomal preparations were individually incubated with 10 μ M FPF as described previously (Haas et al., 2021). Briefly: incubations were carried out in triplicate in 0.1 M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.6) supplemented with an NADPH-regenerating system (Promega, Madison, USA) for 1 h at 25 °C in a total assay volume of 200 μ L containing 80 μ g of microsomal protein. Microsomes incubated without NADPH regeneration system served as controls. Reactions were terminated by the addition of ice-cold acetonitrile (to 80 % final concentration), followed by overnight storage at 4 °C for protein precipitation, and subsequently centrifuged at 3200 \times g for 15 min at 4 °C. The resulting supernatant was analysed by UPLC-MS/MS on an Agilent 1290 Infinity II, a Waters Acquity HSS T3 RP18 column (2.1 \times 50 mm, 1.8 mm) with MeCN/H₂O/1 % formic acid as the eluent in gradient mode. Ion transitions were recorded after positive electrospray ionization on a Sciex API6500 Triple Quad. FPF, FPF-OH, FPF-AF, and FPF-DFEA were measured in positive ion mode (ion transitions: FPF 289 > 126, FPF-OH 305 > 126, FPF-AF 164 > 146, FPF-DFEA 207 > 126). The linear range for the quantification of FPF, FPF-OH, FPF-AF and FPF-DFEA was 1–100 ng/mL, 0.1–20 ng/mL, 0.5–50 ng/mL and 0.1–50 ng/mL, respectively.

3. Results

3.1. Bioassays

Clones 4106A and 37 are highly sensitive to flupyradifurone with LC₅₀ values of 0.286 and 0.382 mg/L respectively (Table 1). The clone 18KarTob03 exhibited modest resistance with a RR of 10.7 while clones 19TyrP02, 20MelP02, 20MelP04B and 5191A were highly resistant with RRs >1300. Finally, extremely high resistance was exhibited by clones 5 and 67, with even flupyradifurone concentrations >5000 mg/L failing to kill 50 % of the tested aphids (e.g. RRs >17483).

To investigate the potential role of P450s in resistance, insecticide bioassays were performed in combination with PBO an inhibitor of cytochrome P450s. This resulted in substantial decreases in LC₅₀ values in all resistant clones (synergism ratios of 11–85) suggesting P450s play a major role in flupyradifurone resistance in *M. persicae*.

3.2. Transcriptomic analysis

To investigate the molecular basis of resistance to flupyradifurone

observed in our *M. persicae* clones, we performed replicated (n = 4) RNA sequencing of the 18KarTob03, 19TyrP02, 37, 5 and 67 clones. We further leveraged existing RNAseq data for clones 4106A and 5191A (Singh et al., 2020). We first investigated the role of target-site mechanisms in resistance by mapping RNAseq data of each clone to the genes encoding nAChR subunits, to identify potential target-site alterations associated with resistance. This revealed the presence of the R81T mutation in the nAChR β 1 subunit that is known to cause resistance to neonicotinoids and cross-resistance to flupyradifurone and sulfoxaflor (see introduction) in clones 5 and 67 in the homozygous or a heterozygote state respectively (Fig. S1). This is consistent with the extremely high levels of resistance to flupyradifurone exhibited by these clones in our insecticide bioassays. No other non-synonymous mutations were identified in these genes that consistently discriminated the resistant and susceptible clones. Furthermore, no significant change in expression of any of the nAChR subunits across all tested clones was identified in differential gene expression analysis (Table S1). Thus, flupyradifurone resistance in the 18KarTob03, 19TyrP02 and 5191A clones does not appear to be associated with modification of the target-site.

To explore the role of metabolic mechanisms in flupyradifurone resistance, we used the RNAseq data to conduct differential gene expression analyses, comparing all resistant clone libraries vs all susceptible clone libraries. This analysis identified 383 genes as differentially expressed at logFC > abs(0.5) and adjusted p-value <0.05, with 251 upregulated in the resistant clones and 132 downregulated (Table S1). Of these, a number of genes known to be involved in insecticide resistance were upregulated, including the P450 genes *CYP6CY3*, *CYP6CY4*, *CYP380C39* and *CYP380C40* (Fig. 1). Of particular note, as genes showing a high mean expression, were *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4*, in which the resistant clones showed 9–17-fold upregulation over the susceptible clones (Fig. 2A and B). Individual comparisons of resistant and susceptible clones further identified the P450 genes *CYP6DA1* and *CYP6DA2* as upregulated specifically in the 18KarTob03 and 19TyrP02 clones (Fig. 2C and D). Independent analysis of the expression of these P450 genes in three flupyradifurone resistant *M. persicae* clones compared to a susceptible clone using qPCR revealed that only *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4* were overexpressed in all resistant clones (Fig. 3). Interrogation of coding sequence variation in these P450 genes revealed a mutation causing a T25I amino acid substitution previously associated with *CYP6CY3* gene duplication (Singh et al., 2020) in all the resistant clones. In combination with the results of synergists bioassays, these findings provide evidence that flupyradifurone resistance may be mediated by the enhanced expression of one or more P450

Table 1
Sensitivity of clones of *M. persicae* to flupyradifurone in dose-response insecticide bioassays in the presence or absence of the synergist PBO.

Clone	Treatment	Slope \pm SE	LC ₅₀ mgL ⁻¹	Confidence intervals (95 %)	df	RR ^a	SR ^b
4106A	Flupyradifurone	2.35 \pm 0.18	0.286	0.244–0.334	6	–	
	Flupyradifurone + PBO	1.30 \pm 0.16	0.076	0.050–0.110	8		3.8
Clone 37	Flupyradifurone	0.86 \pm 0.10	0.380	0.025–4.639	3	1.3	
	Flupyradifurone + PBO	1.02 \pm 0.14	0.062	0.032–0.108	3		6.2
18KarTob03	Flupyradifurone	1.33 \pm 0.12	3.023	2.260–3.960	7	10.6	
	Flupyradifurone + PBO	1.27 \pm 0.14	0.278	0.151–0.436	10		10.9
5191A	Flupyradifurone	1.52 \pm 0.21	392.871	327.368–476.319	7	1373.7	
	Flupyradifurone + PBO	1.05 \pm 0.12	8.805	6.267–12.380	8		44.6
19TyrP02	Flupyradifurone	1.66 \pm 0.17	410.959	320.707–544.137	7	1436.9	
	Flupyradifurone + PBO	1.25 \pm 0.14	4.814	3.250–7.089	9		85.4
Clone 5	Flupyradifurone	–	>5000	–	3	17,483.0	
	Flupyradifurone + PBO	0.84 \pm 0.12	113.109	5.497–525.108	3		44.2
Clone 67	Flupyradifurone	–	>5000	–	3	17,483.0	
	Flupyradifurone + PBO	0.83 \pm 0.10	174.891	88.896–306.094	3		28.6
20MelP02B	Flupyradifurone	2.33 \pm 0.32	496.879	375.765–661.045	6	1737.3	
	Flupyradifurone + PBO	1.81 \pm 0.24	32.812	23.719–45.316	6		15.1
20MelP04	Flupyradifurone	2.27 \pm 0.31	547.282	412.918–734.10	6	1913.6	
	Flupyradifurone + PBO	1.94 \pm 0.25	35.355	25.930–48.207	6		15.5

^a Resistance ratio.

^b Synergism ratio.

^c Data presented in Papadimitriou et al. (2022)

Fig. 1. Normalised read count heatmap of differentially expressed cytochrome P450 genes in flupyradifurone resistant and susceptible *M. persicae* clones. Values are coloured relative to mean read count per gene.

Fig. 2. Normalised read counts of A) *CYP6CY3* B) *CYP6CY4* C) *CYP6DA1* and D) *CYP6DA2* from RNAseq libraries (n = 3–4) from *M. persicae* clones identified as resistant or susceptible to flupyradifurone.

genes.

GO analysis showed enrichment for terms related to DNA biosynthesis and integration in both the upregulated and downregulated datasets, which subsequent investigation suggested represented transposable element activity. Also overrepresented were endopeptidase activity and carboxylesterase activity (Fig. S2A and B).

3.3. Transgenic *Drosophila* expressing *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4* but not other P450s are resistant to flupyradifurone

To functionally investigate the role of the candidate P450 genes identified by transcriptome profiling in flupyradifurone resistance, transgenic lines of *D. melanogaster* were created expressing either *CYP6CY3*, *CYP6CY4*, *CYP380C39*, *CYP380C40*, *CYP6DA1* or *CYP6DA2* (Fig. S3). In dose-response insecticide bioassays lines expressing *CYP380C39*, *CYP380C40*, *CYP6DA1* or *CYP6DA2* exhibited no significant resistance to flupyradifurone compared with control flies of the same genetic background but without a transgene (Fig. 4A, Table S2). In contrast, transgenic *Drosophila* lines expressing *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4* were significantly more tolerant to flupyradifurone ($p < 0.01$) in comparison to the no-transgene control (Fig. 4A–Table S2). These findings were further confirmed by Kaplan-Meier survival analysis of transgenic *Drosophila* lines expressing *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4* exposed to 1800 mg/L flupyradifurone (Fig. 4B). Collectively these findings demonstrate that expression of *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4* is sufficient to confer a modest resistance phenotype to flupyradifurone *in vivo*.

3.4. Heterologously expressed *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4* metabolise flupyradifurone *in vitro*

To functionally characterise the candidate P450 genes identified in this study *in vitro*, each was individually expressed in an insect cell line using the baculovirus system. Of the expressed P450s, only *CYP6CY3*, *CYP6CY4* and *CYP6DA1* showed significant activity against model fluorescent substrates, with *CYP6CY3*, *CYP6CY4* exhibiting good activity against MFC, while *CYP6DA1* effectively metabolised MOBFC (Fig. 4C). We leveraged this activity against model substrates to perform competitive inhibition assays in the presence of flupyradifurone. No significant reduction in the activity of *CYP6DA1* against MOBFC was observed in the presence of even very high concentrations of flupyradifurone. In contrast, the metabolism of MFC by both *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4* was strongly inhibited by flupyradifurone in a dose-dependent manner (calculated IC_{50} values of 458.75 ± 1.10 and 313.06 ± 1.07 μ M respectively, Fig. 4D). To confirm these findings, recombinant *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4* were incubated with flupyradifurone in the presence or absence of NADPH and the results analysed by UPLC-MS/MS. Both *CYP6CY3* and *CYP6CY4* exhibited NADPH-dependent hydroxylation of the furanone moiety of flupyradifurone - resulting in 5-hydroxy flupyradifurone (FPF-OH), with an approximately 10-fold higher amount of this metabolite produced by *CYP6CY3* than *CYP6CY4* (Fig. 4E and F). In the case of *CYP6CY3* we identified a second metabolite, flupyradifurone-difluoroethanamine FPF-DFEA, most likely resulting from the oxidative degradation of the FPF(-OH) furanone moiety (Fig. 4E). We failed to identify flupyradifurone-(difluoroethyl)amino-furanone (FPF-AF)

Fig. 3. Expression levels of six P450 genes in three flupyradifurone resistant clones of *M. persicae* compared to a susceptible clone as determined by qPCR. A) *CYP6CY3*, B) *CYP6CY4*, C) *CYP6DA1*, D) *CYP6DA2*, E) *CYP380C39*, F) *CYP380C40*. Error bars indicate 95 % confidence limits (n = 4) (*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001, ****p < 0.0001, one-way ANOVA and Tukey's post-hoc test).

Fig. 4. Functional characterization of the role of P450s in *M. persicae* resistance to flupyradifurone. A) Sensitivity of transgenic strains of *Drosophila melanogaster* expressing *M. persicae* cytochrome P450s to flupyradifurone (control line comprises flies of the same genetic background to experimental lines but lacking any transgene, see methods for details). Significance (* $p < 0.01$) is referenced against this control line and based on non-overlapping 95 % fiducial limits of LC₅₀ values ($n = 4$). B) Survival analysis of transgenic *Drosophila* lines expressing CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 exposed to 1800 mg/L flupyradifurone compared to a control line of the same genetic background but lacking any transgene (error bars display standard deviation ($n = 4$), difference comparisons were performed in GraphPad Prism v10.3.1 with the log-rank test. *** $p < 0.001$). C) Activity of CYP6CY3, CYP6CY4 and CYP6DA1 against fluorescent coumarin model substrates of MFC and BFC. Error bars display standard deviation ($n = 3$). Abbreviations: MFC, 7-methoxy-4-trifluoromethyl coumarin; BFC, 7-benzyloxy-4-(trifluoromethyl)-coumarin. D) Inhibition of the activity of CYP6CY3, CYP6CY4 and CYP6DA1 against MFC (CYP6CY3, CYP6CY4) or BFC (CYP6DA1) in the presence of increasing concentrations of flupyradifurone (error bars display standard deviation ($n = 3$), *** $p < 0.0001$). E) and F) metabolite production following metabolism of flupyradifurone (FPA) by recombinant CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 respectively. Abbreviations: FPF-AF, FPF-(difluoroethyl)amino-furanone; FPF-OH, FPF-5'hydroxy and FPF-DFEA, FPF-difluoroethanamine. Error bars display standard deviation ($n = 3$).

which has been previously identified as a product of flupyradifurone metabolism by certain bee P450s (Haas et al., 2021). Thus, these results demonstrate that CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 metabolise flupyradifurone *in vitro*, corroborating our *in vivo* data and providing additional evidence of the role of these P450s in resistance to this insecticide.

4. Discussion

Understanding the molecular mechanisms underpinning insecticide

resistance and the cross-resistance profiles conferred by these mechanisms is critical to developing effective resistance management and rational control strategies. In this regard flupyradifurone has been heralded as a particularly useful tool for resistance management and integrated pest management, as it is not compromised by certain pre-existing resistance mechanisms to older insecticides present in specific pest insect species (Nauen et al., 2015). However, here we confirm the results of previous studies (Papadimitriou et al., 2022) by revealing high levels of resistance to flupyradifurone in *M. persicae*, including in a clone

that predates the registration of this insecticide. We provide evidence that resistance is mediated by a target-site and metabolic component, and show that a pre-existing resistance mechanism in *M. persicae* provides cross-resistance to flupyradifurone. Our findings provide insight into the molecular mechanisms underpinning resistance to insecticides and the evolution of insecticide cross-resistance and have implications for the sustainable control of a global crop pest.

Our data provide several lines of evidence that resistance to flupyradifurone in *M. persicae* is conferred by the P450s CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 including: i) strong synergism of flupyradifurone toxicity by the P450 inhibitor piperonyl butoxide in resistant clones of *M. persicae*, ii) enhanced expression of CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 in resistant clones, iii) flupyradifurone resistance in transgenic *D. melanogaster* expressing these P450s, and, iv) metabolism of flupyradifurone by recombinant CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 *in vitro*.

The discovery of the role of P450s in flupyradifurone resistance in *M. persicae* has parallels with previous work. Early work on flupyradifurone mode of action indicated that, in *B. tabaci*, the P450 CYP6CM1 overexpressed in neonicotinoid resistant populations is not involved in its metabolism (Jeschke et al., 2015; Nauen et al., 2015). Instead, field evolved resistance to flupyradifurone in this species appears to be mediated by a different P450 enzyme, CYP6CX4, confirmed through RNAi and expression in transgenic *D. melanogaster* (Zhang et al., 2024). In western honeybees, *Apis mellifera*, flupyradifurone is metabolised by 3 different enzymes, CYP6AQ1, CYP9Q2 and CYP9Q3 (Haas et al., 2021), demonstrating, as in our study, the role of multiple P450s with overlapping substrate specificity in resistance. Interestingly, CYP9Q2 and CYP9Q3 are also important molecular determinants of honeybee acute sensitivity to certain types of neonicotinoids (Manjon et al., 2018), revealing partial overlap between metabolism of neonicotinoids and butenolides. Recent work has also shown that the ability to metabolise flupyradifurone is conserved across all major bee pollinator families with functional orthologs of these CYP9Q and CYP6AQ P450s (Haas et al., 2022; Xiao et al., 2023). Thus, in combination with our results, these findings demonstrate that P450s play a key role in mediating resistance to flupyradifurone across diverse insect species. The phylogenetic relationship between these P450s is illustrated in Fig. S4.

The enhanced expression of CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 in flupyradifurone resistant *M. persicae* clones identified in this study does not represent a *de novo* mutation following the introduction of this insecticide. Rather, as illustrated by the upregulation of these P450s (and high levels of flupyradifurone resistance) in *M. persicae* clone 5191A collected in Greece in 2007, the overexpression of these P450s predates the registration of flupyradifurone in Greece (2018). Previous research has shown that CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 overexpression evolved to allow *M. persicae* to detoxify the plant secondary metabolite nicotine and utilise tobacco as a host. This process was mediated by gene amplification, with both CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 part of a large segmental duplication (Bass et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2020). Additional duplication of CYP6CY3, expansion of a microsatellite polymorphism in the promoter region of this gene, and multiple insertions of transposable elements at the gene locus further enhanced the expression of this P450 in the gut of resistant aphid clones to levels >2500-fold greater than in susceptible clones (Singh et al., 2020). These findings suggest that CYP6CY3 may play a particularly important role in xenobiotic resistance. We observed a significant spread in the level of expression, of CYP6CY3, in flupyradifurone resistant clones. This likely reflects clone-specific gene copy number variation, structural locus diversity or an involvement of an unknown *trans*-acting factor. Further work is required to resolve the relative contribution of these factors in modulating CYP6CY3 in resistant clones.

The fact that enhanced expression of CYP6CY3 has preadapted *M. persicae* to tolerate flupyradifurone is notable as the overexpression of this P450 has also been shown to confer resistance to at least four different synthetic neonicotinoid insecticides and nicotine (Nakao et al., 2019). The finding that CYP6CY3 can confer cross-resistance to diverse

insecticides suggests this P450 may play a key role in protecting *M. persicae* from environmental xenobiotics. Unfortunately, such cross-resistance is problematic for resistance management efforts, such as those based on the rotation of insecticides. Specifically, in this scenario applications of one insecticide can select for aphid genotypes with a resistance mutation conferring resistance to both the insecticide applied and others cross-resisted by that mechanism. In this regard, a highly significant positive association was found between resistance to the neonicotinoid acetamiprid and flupyradifurone in field populations of *M. persicae* in Greece, suggesting application of acetamiprid had selected for genotypes that are cross-resistant to flupyradifurone (Papadimitriou et al., 2022).

In our study the presence of the R81T substitution in the β 1 subunit of nAChR in *M. persicae* clones overexpressing CYP6CY3 and CYP6CY4 appears to have a strong synergistic effect on the overall level of flupyradifurone resistance. Indeed, this combination of target-site and metabolic mechanisms is associated with essential immunity to flupyradifurone. These findings are consistent with a previous study of *M. persicae* populations in Greece which found that R81T was partially associated with resistance to flupyradifurone (Papadimitriou et al., 2022). Future work is required to unpick the relative contribution of R81T and P450 overexpression to resistance. However, our bioassay data indicate that even the presence of R81T in the heterozygous form is enough to significantly strengthen the resistant phenotype. This is consistent with the finding that the R81T mutation is inherited as a semi-recessive trait in terms of resistance to thiacloprid in *M. persicae* (Mottet et al., 2024). Further insight into the resistance conferred by R81T in isolation has also been provided by research using CRISPR-Cas genome editing. Specifically, a genome edited strain of *D. melanogaster* carrying R81T in the homozygous form exhibited only low (6.5) to moderate (32.6) resistance ratios to acetamiprid and imidacloprid, and only 6.9-fold resistance to flupyradifurone. Flies heterozygous for R81T only showed 1.9-fold resistance to flupyradifurone (Homem et al., 2020). This suggests that resistance conferred by this mechanism in isolation is modest. Finally, recent work on the relative contributions of R81T and CYP6CY genes to neonicotinoid resistance in *M. persicae* showed a strong synergistic effect between the two mechanisms, with a strong correlation between CYP expression and the resistant phenotype (Mottet et al., 2024). As hypothesised by others (Samantsidis et al., 2020), the reduction in binding affinity to the receptor caused by the point mutation may provide more time for enzymatic detoxification of the insecticide.

While our results, in combination with previous work, reveal key mechanisms underlying resistance to flupyradifurone it is possible that other genes contribute to the resistance phenotypes observed in *M. persicae*. Specifically, bioassays using the P450 inhibitor PBO failed to restore full susceptibility to flupyradifurone in the resistant clones of *M. persicae* tested in this study – including those without the R81T mutation. We further identified enrichment for carboxylesterase activity in the gene set shown to be significantly upregulated in resistant clones. Thus, future investigation of the role of these and other detoxification gene families in resistance, such as glutathione S-transferases and UDP-glucosyltransferases, is warranted.

In conclusion, our data reveal that a pre-existing mechanism of resistance to nicotine and neonicotinoids in *M. persicae* confers cross-resistance to flupyradifurone. Given the high frequency of CYP6CY3/4 overexpression in global populations of this species (Singh et al., 2021), it will be important to consider these findings in the development of future resistance and integrated pest management strategies. For example, ensuring that the use of flupyradifurone and neonicotinoids against *M. persicae* is, i) informed by contemporary sensitivity data and/or the use of molecular diagnostics against the mechanisms described in our study, and, ii) a component of strategies involving other insecticides of different mode of action and/or non-insecticidal control methods.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jun Yuan: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Bin Zeng:** Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Benjamin J. Hunt:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Bartłomiej J. Troczka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision. **Xingzhi Xiao:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **James Gardner:** Methodology, Investigation. **Faye Papadimitriou:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Jason Charamis:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Aris Ilias:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Adam Pym:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Konstantinos Mavridis:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Dieudonné T. Tshitenge:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ralf Nauen:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **John Vontas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **John T. Margaritopoulos:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Xianhui Yin:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Chris Bass:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Data curation.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibmb.2026.104487>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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